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Denmark-US students' collaboration as a part of ambiguous interdisciplinary engineering design courses

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INTRODUCTION

The paper describes experiences from the first two successful international projects. The work is focused on project management, project planning, communication, and cultural and language differences during the endeavors. The project relevant phases are presented from the instructors' perspectives and from students' points of view. Developing and planning of common projects in engineering education often give more practical challenges, such as how to deal with engineering programs' differences on the international level, in addition to well-expected differences in engineering fields. Other major challenges are the variations in academic calendar and the amount of credits given for courses in different universities, programs, and countries. There is also a difference in time zones that needed to be considered for this scenario. A special part of the paper is focused on the experience in arranging face-to-face

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meetings and common activities in order to facilitate and enhance students' communication, engagement, and understanding of different cultures. Analysis of students' own opinions of these projects concludes the paper.

In 2017, cooperation between the Section for Electrical Technology at the Technical University of Denmark, Center for Bachelor of Engineering Studies (DTU Diplom) and the Aeronautical Engineering Technology (AET) program of the School of Aviation and Transportation Technology (SATT), Purdue University in the USA was established. The main purpose of the collaboration was to bring together students from different academic programs and cultures [1,2,3] to perform interdisciplinary work [4,5], which is highly relevant for all engineers, and to gain experience with international teamwork. Both competencies are highly required in high technology companies around the world [6,7].

Purdue University focuses on aviation and educates engineers and engineering technology graduates for the aeronautical industry. Purdue uses its own airport (which includes a collection of airplanes and aircraft engines and other components) for teaching and research. The SATT also prepares managers specializing in aviation and educates commercial pilots. The cooperative projects for students from DTU Diplom (Technical University of Denmark, Campus Ballerup) are based on an actual need of the school to modernize and possibly digitize test equipment when running tests on their PT-6 engine. The first project ran in fall 2017 and the second project in spring 2018. There were two tasks for the projects:

1. to digitize a checklist carried out when running tests via a mobile app
2. to collect sensors' data to continuous output to LabView.

The overall foci for the cooperation and the projects were project definition, project management, planning, process improvement, and communication between two teams from different backgrounds, both in an academic and in international perspective. This project work gives DTU students ten ECTS credits and is considered a project similar to the course called "Innovation Pilot" [8], which is a special DTU Diplom course focusing on innovation in engineering and technology. For Purdue students, their project counts as a second part (second semester) of their senior capstone project and students get up to six credit hours. The credit systems are different in USA and in Europe, but it was found that the workload for both courses was comparable.

1 TECHNICAL PROBLEM STATEMENT

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2 COMMUNICATION IN INTERDISCIPLINARY TEAMS

Efficient communication in an organization, which in the projects was a combination of the students from Denmark and USA, is a decisive factor on how well an organization will function. The need for information and knowledge exchange grows as a project progresses, and this in turn increases the demand for frequent and systematic communication coordination. Teams of engineers from different branches of the engineering fields work together to develop solutions to complex technical problems [9,10]. This requires communication/language including professional terminology from different areas, such as electronics, mechanics, and computer engineering. Therefore, it is essential for us to train students to communicate and convey academic knowledge in a meaningful way to engineers from different technical fields. The projects put a large focus on communication and the common challenges of communication between interdisciplinary and international teams. Additional obstacles in communication are physical distance and time difference. Specifically, certain challenges arise in what are called virtual organizations: organizations which conduct business and communicate entirely via digital means. In the following, we will discuss the challenges that arise when using certain lines of communication.

2.1 Lines of communication

Establishing the lines of communication between two parties and deciding who was responsible for them were essential in how well the development of the project would go. In the international projects between teams separated by an ocean, the choice of lines of communication was critical for the project results.

2.2 E-mail communication

The obvious choice was to use e-mail as the main form of communication. At the start of the project, especially, this was the best way to communicate. However, this soon led to various complications:

- Communicating via e-mail was slow: Communication via e-mail slowed the process of exchanging information. It took an average of five to six days for each team to respond to a request. This had adverse effects for both teams: it inhibited the efficiency of the development process and it served as a source of frustration for both teams, leading to conflicts.
- Communication via e-mail was signal-poor: E-mail as a communication medium lacks details. Face-to-face communication, which is signal-rich, enables faster feedback, utilization of natural (spoken) language, and allows the sender and the recipient to communicate in a personal manner. These are all elements which e-mail clearly lacks.

However, communicating via e-mail did have some positive effects:

- Communication via e-mail enabled parallel communication: Communicating via e-mail enabled a sender to communicate with many at the same time. It is a parallel form of communication, which the teams utilized to their advantage. One sender could inform all parties (also external interest groups, like professors and advisors) of what was going on.
- Communication via e-mail served as an implicit way of documenting the process: Writing e-mails to one another served as a way of documenting the process from beginning to end. In the beginning of the project, both teams used this feature of communicating and documenting.

3 VISIT TO THE USA

During the first project (fall 2017) the DTU team came to visit the Purdue team about 1.5 months after the project started. This meeting was significant because it elevated the efficiency of the project development and spoke to all the aforementioned theories about the importance of creating a feeling of togetherness between two groups with no prior knowledge or relationship with one another. Within one day after arrival, the Purdue team invited the DTU team to lunch and to watch football in their homes. This had a huge effect on the way both groups started to interact with one another. Having learned from this experience, a similar visit was arranged just two weeks after the second project (spring 2018) started.

The effects of the visits to Purdue where both teams met in person are many. They showed that it is extremely important to establish personal connections with the people you work with through socialization. Meeting each other and creating a common background through shared experiences make it easier to develop the technical solutions and common desire for mutual success in the project work. Furthermore, because the team members met and socialized with each other, the way they communicated after the visits became more efficient.

4 CHALLENGES IN TEAMS WORKING PHYSICALLY SEPARATED

A virtual organization is an organization which is physically separated and therefore will communicate and problem solve via digital means [11]. The team members in our projects were all members of a virtual organization because they never met in person and they only communicated via digital means.

Studies show that virtual groups sometimes work more efficiently than normal groups, but in certain situations virtual groups do not work well. This is especially true under the following conditions:

- The group members have no prior relationship to each other
- The project involves certain risk
- There is no fundamental trust between the group members

When these factors are present in virtual groups, the exchanged information will frequently be misinterpreted and the members of their respective groups will be selective with what information is shared with the other group. This basically translates to a less efficient group as a whole, where the suboptimal lines of communication hinder the project development.

In the projects described, all of the named factors were present. The group members had no prior knowledge or relationship with one another and the projects involved a certain amount of risk for both groups, translating to both teams having a personal interest in succeeding and wanting to affect the trajectory of the project development. Both teams therefore experienced the more adverse effects that virtual groups carry with it, like slow e-mail communication and communication prone to misinterpretation (misunderstandings happened frequently) and both parties had a tendency to withhold information that, if had they known each other, would have been shared. However, the students did try to compensate for this after their visits to Purdue. Both student teams, independently of each other, wanted to switch to a more dynamic way of communicating by combining e-mail, video conferencing, and instant messaging.

5 PROJECT MANAGEMENT

The Lean Six Sigma methodology could be viewed as a combination of the data-driven Tollgate Project approach and variation reduction of Six Sigma and the reduction of waste by using Lean principles [12]. This blending of Lean and Six Sigma is considerable because they both strive to improve performance and pursue perfection [13]. Lean Six Sigma is widely used in the aerospace industry, as well in a widespread range of other types of companies and government agencies [14,15]. Lean Six Sigma is being used in every aspect of business, starting from design and manufacturing and finishing with supply chain processes. As an example, Lockheed Martin developed a method called LM21 (Lockheed Martin in the 21st Century) in 1999. The idea was to deliver excellence to employees, customers, and shareholders through the best approach. Lean Six Sigma became a management philosophy, affecting the whole company: operations, finance, and cash management [16]. Another example is a problem that Boeing had with recirculating air fans rejected during testing for its 777 program. The solution was to eliminate possibilities of foreign object debris entering during assembly [17]. It showed that Lean Six Sigma can't be ignored in the preparation of future engineers. This is why it was chosen as a one of the major components of the projects described [18,19].

6 CONCLUSION

Cooperation between DTU Diplom and Purdue University resulted in joint student projects, where engineering students from Denmark and USA worked together to find solutions for technical interdisciplinary problems. During the projects students had the possibility not only to train their technical skills, but also to develop their understanding of other fields of engineering, enhance their communication and language skills,

broaden their cultural understanding, and grow in their ability to work in team with other team members who were physically away and in another time zone.

Meeting and working with students from another country was quite a new experience for both Danish and US students, even though there are not big cultural differences between the USA and Denmark. Especially for American students, it was an eye opener to learn about other nations, languages, and cultures. Many American students had not visited Europe before. Many Danish students had usually travel to other European countries before and some of them had been in countries all over the world, but they had not experienced the personal contact, socialization, and living in each other homes like they did during the project. This gave them quite a unique experience and the opportunity to better understand the way other cultures think and work.

The technical scope of both projects has been accomplished with very promising results. A mobile application was developed to run on an Android device and the reading of sensors has been implemented with Arduino and software applications to make it possible to visualize the results on computer or tablet. The cooperation and projects prepared both Danish and US students for their future work in international companies with international and interdisciplinary teams.

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